

Medium effect on deprotonation equilibrium of HA-type acid-indicators in aqueous NaNO_3 solutions – a model aquo-ionic system

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Abstract : The saturated solubility and the indicator constant of four newly synthesized HA-type azo-dye acid indicators, have been determined in NaNO_3 aquo-ionic model solvent system. The relative dissociation equilibrium of HA is found to be a function of transfer Gibb's energy of all the involved species in equilibrium for each indicator, although it is mainly dictated by that of conjugate anion A^- . The greater stability of the oxo anion A^- of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diaminoazo benzene with respect to other indicators due to increasing interaction with the solvated Na^+ ions with increased NaNO_3 concentration, differentiates it from others.

Keywords : Acid indicators, equilibrium, NaNO_3 , aquo-ionic system.

Introduction

In order to understand the deprotonation equilibrium properties of four synthesized azo-dyes after using them successfully as acid-base indicators^{1,2} in a model aquo-ionic system³⁻⁵, solubility and indicator constant (dissociation constant) of the dyes have been determined in a few concentrated aqueous NaNO_3 solutions spectrophotometrically. Notably, highly concentrated salt solutions are expected to behave in a completely different and more interesting manner as compared to pure water, dilute aqueous salt solutions and aquo-organic solvent systems⁶, in reference to the equilibrium and kinetics of different types of chemical systems including that involved proton transfer equilibrium. Thermodynamic studies in concentrated salt solutions are quite extensive⁷⁻¹² and really important. This is because that the most part of the surface on earth is screened with salty sea-water. The living cells – the primary unit of life, reside and respond in the atmosphere of concentrated salt solutions. Therefore, in these vast and important material areas, numerous reactions accomplish everyday. So, the studies of model aqua-ionic systems are really expedient and in evitable in order to understand these important reactions and materials. Here model aqua-ionic solvent system taken is aqueous NaNO_3 solutions of strength 1(m) to 4(m). Lack of the sufficient relevant data in aqueous NaCl solutions to evaluate the individual contributions of the involved species to the

medium effect on dissociation of indicator acid HA, leads us to select here NaNO_3 instead of NaCl as a model aqueous ionic co-solvent⁷⁻¹². So, the dissociation constant (K_A) and solubility (s) of the four synthesized HA type dyes (HI_n) have been determined in 1–4 (m) aqueous NaNO_3 solutions in order to understand the equilibrium acid base properties in a model aqua-ionic systems in terms of the relative stability of the species involved in the reactions. The experimentally determined values of S and K_A in conjugation help us to compute the standard transfer Gibbs energies ($\Delta G_{(\text{HA})}^{0,\text{N}}$) of the species involved in the equilibrium :

in differently concentrated salt solutions in reference to pure water. The study of newly synthesized azo-dye indicator used are 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene (I_1), 2-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene (I_2), 2-(2'-nitrophenyl)-azo-1-naphthol (I_3) and 4-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene (I_4) respectively.

Transfer Gibb's energy ($\Delta G^{0,\text{N}}$) values of H^+ , I_n^- and undissociated HI_n seem to reflect the interactions of Na^+ and NO_3^- with them and the relative stability of them in NaNO_3 aqua-ionic system in comparison to pure water and thus the guiding factor in the equilibria. The study also helps to distinguish the different indicators synthesized, in reference to their deprotonation equilibria.

Experimental

Materials :

Sodium nitrate (A.R.) was used after drying at 423 K and cooling then in a vacuum desiccator for 10 h. All the indicators were re-crystallized from alcohol-water mixture and dried in a vacuum desiccator before use. Water used was triply distilled. Solvents viz. aqueous NaNO₃ solutions of various concentration employed in this present study were prepared by mixing the components by weight. HCl (A.R., Glaxo) and NaOH (G.R., Merck) were used as received.

The absorbances of differently concentrated aqueous solution of the indicators have been recorded with Systronics UV-Visible spectrophotometer at the determined λ_{\max} and plotted against concentration for all the indicators to evaluate molar extinction coefficient values in pure water. The solubilities of four indicators studied in water, 1(m), 2(m) and 4(m) aqueous NaNO₃ solution have been determined with the help of molar extinction coefficient values. Saturated solubilities of the indicators in water and in the aqua-ionic solvents have been determined by taking ~0.01 g of each of the indicators in separate test tubes followed by addition of a given solvent like water or aqueous NaNO₃ solution, enclosed with standard-joint stopper, shaken well and then allowed to equilibrate in a thermostat at 308.15 K for 24 h. A small measured volume of the filtered saturated solution of each indicator in a given solvent has been taken out after equilibration and the absorbance has been measured at λ_{\max} . This measurement part of the experiment has been done for two or three times until a constant value of solubility within $\pm 1\%$ is obtained. The same experiment has also been done for each aqueous NaNO₃ solution for all the indicators studied.

Solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid each of 1 M strength were made by dissolving in water, 1(m), 2(m) and 4(m) aqueous NaNO₃ solution 0.001% indicator solution (I₁-I₄) were obtained by dissolving requisite amounts in 2 : 1 alcohol and water mixtures. Lachman and Polstan procedure^{13,14} for the pK_{In} determination has been adopted here. The two concentrated solutions of NaOH and HCl were used. Solutions of different pH values were adjusted by addition of small volume of concentrated solutions by micropipette. The apparent pK_{In} values have been determined using Henderson-Hasselbach equation applicable for spectrometric titration.

Results and discussion

The dissociation constant (K_{In}) of the acid indicators in pure water and aqua-ionic solvents were determined by measuring the absorbances of each indicator in buffer solution of different pH (d_{buffer}) and that at very high and low pH (d_{acid} and d_{base} respectively) in each solvent pK_{In} is obtained from a linear plot of pH vs

$$\log \frac{(d_{\text{buffer}} - d_{\text{acid}})}{(d_{\text{base}} - d_{\text{buffer}})}$$
 from the intercept according to the

equation,

$$\text{pH} = \text{pK}_{In} + \log \frac{(d_{\text{buffer}} - d_{\text{acid}})}{(d_{\text{base}} - d_{\text{buffer}})} \quad (1)$$

The observed saturated solubilities (s) in mol dm⁻³ at 308.15 K are plotted in Table 1. To compute mean molal activity co-efficient different solvent parameters viz. sol-

Table 1. The values of Debye-Huckel constant A_0B_0 , B_0 and the related solvent parameters at 308.15 K

Types of solution	$d_s \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/dm ⁻³)	ϵ (35 °C)	A_0B_0 (mol ^{-1/2} kg ^{1/2})	$B_0 \times 10^7$ (mol ^{-1/2} kg ^{1/2})
0(m)	0.99406	74.85	1.198	330.416
1(m)	1.0454	68.40	1.404	354.121
2(m)	1.0931	60.20	1.740	386.171
4(m)	1.1764	48.40	2.504	446.719

vent densities (d_s) and di-electric constant (ϵ_s) of the differently concentrated NaNO₃ solution at 308.15 K was taken from the literature^{7,15}. The Debye-Huckel constant A_0B_0 and B_0 values at 308.15 K were evaluated by using eqs. (2) and (3).

$$A_0B_0 = 2.303 \times 1.8246 \times 10^6 \times d_s^{1/2} (\epsilon_s T)^{-3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2} \text{ kg}^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$B_0 = 50.29 \times 10^{10} \times d_s^{1/2} (\epsilon_s T)^{-1/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2} \text{ kg}^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

These values were listed in Table 2. The degree of dissociation of the ion pairs (α) and the mean molar activity coefficient (γ_{\pm}) of all the indicators in water and 1(m), 2(m) and 4(m) aqueous NaNO₃ solution at 308.15 K have been evaluated by iterative method by using eqs. (4) and (5). The K_A in eq. (3) represents dissociation constant of indicator.

$$\alpha = \frac{-1 \pm (1 + 4S.K_A.\gamma_{\pm}^2)^{1/2}}{2.S.K_A.\gamma_{\pm}^2} \quad (4)$$

$$-\ln \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{A_0 B_0 d_s^{-1/2} (\alpha.S)^{1/2}}{2}$$

$$[\{1 + a_+^0 B_0 d_s^{-1/2} (\alpha.S)^{1/2}\}^{-1} + \{1 + a_-^0 B_0 d_s^{-1/2} (\alpha.S)^{1/2}\}^{-1}]$$

$$+ \ln \frac{d_c - 0.001(\alpha.S)M_s + 0.002(\alpha.S)M_w}{d_0} \quad (5)$$

where, the values of the ion size parameters have been taken as 0.3 and 0.5 manometers for a_+^0 and a_-^0 respectively^{16,17}.

The values of solubility product (K_{sp}), and so pK_{sp} , of these four indicators in water and in different aqua-ionic solvents at 308.15 K have been measured by using eq. (6).

$$pK_{sp} = -2 (\log \alpha.S \gamma_{\pm}) \quad (6)$$

The solubility of the indicators (s), indicator constant (pK_{In}), association constants of the ion pair (K_A), degree of dissociation of the ion pairs (α), mean molar activity coefficient (γ_{\pm}) and solubility product have been presented in Table 2.

The result shows that the dissociation of each indicator acid (electrolyte) increases with increase in the con-

centration of $NaNO_3$ as expected due to increased ion-ion interaction.

To enlighten the ionic-solvent effect on dissociation equilibrium of the indicators relative to that in water, the difference in the free energy change of the dissociation equilibrium with respect to the reference solvent, $\Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N}$, have been computed on mole fraction scale by using eq. (6).

$$\Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N} = 2.303 RT [pK_{sp}(s) - pK_{sp}(w)] + 2 \times 2.303 RT \log \frac{M_w.d_s}{M_s.d_w} \quad (7)$$

where M_w and M_s are the molar and mean molar mass of water and the co-solvent respectively in Table 1.

The standard free energy change for undissociated HA in mole fraction scale, $\Delta G_{i(undissociated HA)}^{0,N}$ when 1 mole of indicator (I_1, I_2, I_3 and I_4) is transferred from reference solvent water to differently concentrated (molal) $NaNO_3$ solution at 308.15 K were done by using eqs. (8) and (9).

$$\Delta G^{0,N} = -RT \ln (1 - \alpha)S \quad (8)$$

$$\text{So, } \Delta G_{i(undissociated HA)}^{0,N} = {}_s\Delta G^{0,N} - {}_w\Delta G^{0,N}$$

$$= RT \ln \frac{(1 - \alpha_w)s_w}{(1 - \alpha_s)s_s} + 2.303 RT \log \frac{M_w.d_s}{M_s.d_w} \quad (9)$$

Table 2. Dissociation constants (pK_{In}), solubilities (s, mol dm^{-3}), degree of association (α), mean molar activity coefficient (γ_{\pm}), solubility products (pK_{sp}) in (molar scale) of four synthesized indicator acids in $NaNO_3$ solution at 308.15 K

Indicator	Types of solution	Solubility (s, mol dm^{-3}) $\times 10^4$	pK_{In}	γ_{\pm}	pK_{sp}	α
I_1	Aqueous	1.126	6.73	0.9975	10.695	0.040
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	1.817	6.22	0.9956	9.989	0.056
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	2.706	5.98	0.9934	9.600	0.059
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	4.583	5.71	0.9759	9.073	0.065
I_2	Aqueous	0.236	7.78	0.9991	12.425	0.026
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	0.277	7.42	0.9986	12.004	0.036
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	0.282	7.32	0.9982	11.875	0.041
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	0.284	7.26	0.9949	11.831	0.043
I_3	Aqueous	0.126	7.55	0.9992	12.474	0.046
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	0.159	7.21	0.9988	12.042	0.060
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	0.163	7.18	0.9983	11.978	0.063
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	0.168	7.04	0.9979	11.849	0.071
I_4	Aqueous	0.244	7.71	0.9982	12.332	0.028
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	0.264	7.36	0.9972	11.955	0.040
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	0.272	7.27	0.9964	11.867	0.043
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	0.276	7.21	0.9948	11.797	0.046

A set of $\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N}$ are obtained from a series of known values of $\Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N}$, and literature values of $\Delta G_{i(H^+)}^{0,N}$ in the different media as obtained by the following equation.

$$\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N} = \Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N} - \Delta G_{i(H^+)}^{0,N} \quad (10)$$

The transfer energy values of the individual species involved in the dissociation equilibrium have been listed in Table 3.

for their stabilities are almost similar. I_1 exists as zwitterions whereas I_2 - I_4 forms such zwitterions by resonance due to possible induction by the highly ionic solutions. Since the solvent system is ionic in character, each indicator ion, I^- , is more stabilized than the corresponding neutral indicator, I , as evident from their $\Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N}$ and $\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N}$ values. From this study it can be inferred that

Table 3. The values of standard free energy change $d\Delta G_{diss}^{0,N}$, $\Delta G_{i(undissociated HA)}^{0,N}$, $\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N}$ for I_1 - I_4 indicator when 1 mole of indicator is transferred from reference solvent water to differently concentrated (molal) $NaNO_3$ solution at 308 15 K

Indicator	Types of solution	$d\Delta G_{diss}^{0,N}$ (kJ/mol)	$\Delta G_{i(undissociated HA)}^{0,N}$ (kJ/mol)	$\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N}$ (kJ/mol)
I_1	Pure water	0	0	0
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	-3.042	-1.217	-4.832
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	-4.492	-2.262	-8.296
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	-4.986	-3.668	-12.445
I_2	Pure water	0	0	0
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.167	-0.418	-3.151
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.781	-0.464	-5.082
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	-3.207	-0.569	-6.383
I_3	Pure water	0	0	0
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.039	-0.592	-3.216
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.251	-0.687	-4.763
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	-3.148	-0.813	-6.566
I_4	Pure water	0	0	0
	1(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.098	-0.204	-2.891
	2(m) $NaNO_3$	-2.664	-0.307	-4.580
	4(m) $NaNO_3$	-3.089	-0.408	-6.035

Thus the solvent effect of dissociation equilibria of the indicator would be dictated by the relative solvation of all three involved species.

So, from the values of $\Delta G_{i(HA)}^{0,N}$, $\Delta G_{i(undissociated HA)}^{0,N}$ and $\Delta G_{i(A^-)}^{0,N}$ it is clearly evident that all the four indicators get extra stability in $NaNO_3$ solutions of different concentration with respect to that in water. I_1 gets maximum stability whereas magnitude of stabilities of I_2, I_3, I_4 are very close but general order of stability is : $I_3 > I_2 > I_4$ (Fig. 1).

From the Fig. 1 it is quite evident that I_1^- is much more stabilized than I^- of other indicators whose order of stabilization are almost similar. Similarly the stability of indicator I_1 is much greater than other indicators (I_2 - I_4). Moreover such stabilizations of the indicators and their anions increase with increase of the ionic character of the solvents, I_2 and I_4 are isomers and I_3 also possesses similar structure and resonances with that of I_2 and I_4 . There-

Fig. 1. Plot of $\delta\Delta G_{diss}^0$ I_1, I_2, I_3 and I_4 in differently concentrated $NaNO_3$ solution.

indicator I_1 can also be used in salt solutions for acid-base analytical purposes.

Fig. 1 reveals that the acid dissociation equilibria of all the indicators studied which are favoured with gradual increase of ionic character of aqueous NaNO_3 system. It is also quite evident from the solubility data presented in Table 2, that all the indicators get extra stability in differently concentrated NaNO_3 solutions as reflected by the greater solubility of them in salt solutions with respect to that in water. Among the different acids studied, I_1 gets maximum solubility whereas that of I_2 , I_3 and I_4 are very close. The general order of stability of them in the whole composition range follows the sequence : $I_1 > I_4 > I_2 > I_3$. Since any dissociation equilibrium is expected to be dictated by the relative stability of all the involved species participating in the equilibrium, the difference in the standard Gibb's energy change of the process in given solvent with respect to that in water, $d\Delta G_{\text{diss}}^{0,N}$ are dissected into the contributions of the individual species viz. that of H^+ , A^- and unionized HA. The profiles for the transfer Gibb's energy of the involved species together with $d\Delta G_{\text{diss}}^{0,N}$ against composition of NaNO_3 , have been presented in Figs. 1 and 2 for I_1 and I_3 indicators respectively. For indicators I_2 and I_4 , different profiles quite resemble with that for I_3 and therefore can be understood

from the corresponding profiles for indicator I_3 . The profiles of Figs. 1 and 2 indicate that all the acid dissociation equilibria are more favoured with the increased NaNO_3 content in aquo-ionic solvents mainly due to relatively larger stabilization of conjugate anion A^- than that of the other species involved. The relative destabilization of H^+ as evident by gradual increase of $\delta(\Delta G^0)$ and the relative stabilization of HA as evident by gradual increase of $-d\Delta G_{\text{diss}}^{0,N}$ and the relative stabilization of HA evidenced by gradual decrease of $\Delta G_{\text{t(HA)}}^{0,N}$. Similar observation is also found for other indicators, I_2 and I_4 . The acid-dissociation equilibrium is more favoured for I_1 , than other three indicators (Fig. 1), since the relative stability of A^- with respect to neutral HA is much greater for I_1 than that of other three indicators, as evident from their $\Delta G_{\text{t(HA)}}^{0,N}$ values. A deeper insight of the profiles of Figs. 1 and 2 reveal that the relative Gibb's energy change of the acid dissociation equilibria for indicator I_1 and I_3 , are increasingly negative since the conjugate effect of increased $\Delta G_{\text{t}^+}^{0,N}$ of H^+ and decreased $\Delta G_{\text{t(HA)}}^{0,N}$ of undissociated HA molecule is over come by the increased stability of A^- as evident by the increasingly negative $\Delta G_{\text{t(A}^-)}^{0,N}$ as the con-

Fig. 2. Plot of $\Delta G_{\text{t(HA)}}^{0,N}$, $\Delta G_{\text{t(undissociated HA)}}^{0,N}$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t(A}^-)}^{0,N}$ for I_1 , I_2 , I_3 and I_4 in differently concentrated NaNO_3 solution.

centration of NaNO_3 is increased in the aquo-ionic solvent system studied. This fact is observed for indicators I_2 and I_4 also. The hydronium ion, H_3O^+ is increasingly destabilized in the system due to the withdrawal of significant number of water molecules in the solvation of the ions, leaving lesser number of free water molecules with decreased activity. Thus H_3O^+ finds less water molecules for its solvation, in contrast to its intrinsic structural similarity with and hence stability in water. Moreover hydrated $(\text{Na}^+)_{\text{aqua}}$ occupies much greater volume than that of NO_3^- which is comparatively less hydrated^{18,19}. So the effect of repulsion of more protonic H_2O molecules in the hydrated cosphere, $(\text{Na}^+)_{\text{aq}}$ seems to exceed the attractive interaction of H_3O^+ with NO_3^- . The observed increased stabilization of conjugate anions therefore suggests that the superimposed attractive interaction of A^- and $(\text{Na}^+)_{\text{aq}}$ over the repulsive interaction of A^- and NO_3^- exceeds the interaction between A^- and H_2O molecule in pure water. This is due to more protonic character of H_2O molecule in the hydration cosphere around Na^+ than that in pure water²⁰.

The observed increased stabilization of undissociated indicator acid, HA indicates dipolar character of the neutral acids. I_1 forms zwitterion (Fig. 3) while I_2 , I_3 and I_4 contain dipolar $-\text{NO}_2$ group (Fig. 4) which are stabilized by ionic mixed solvent, aqueous NaNO_3 . Since electron density capability of sp^3 hybridized M is greater than that of a sp^2 hybridized M, I_1 is expected to form more zwitterion than any of the other indicators, I_2 – I_4 .

So all the undissociated indicators with a special references to I_1 , are more stable in environments of increased ionic character as evident from Figs. 1 and 3. All the indicator anions A^- are however increasingly more stable than their corresponding neutral HA at different composition as the solvent system becomes increasingly ionic in character. The relative stability of the anions are in the order : $\text{A}^-(I_4) > \text{A}^-(I_3) > \text{A}^-(I_2) > \text{A}^-(I_1)$, as evident from the reverse order of $\Delta G_{\text{I},\text{N}}^{0,\text{N}}$ of the anions as illustrated by the corresponding profiles in Fig. 4. This is due to the fact that the conjugate anion A^- of I_1 , can delocalise its charge through resonance of carboxylate anion and also through intra-molecular hydrogen bonding forming two six member ring structures thus by creating multipoles or delocalization. An increase in the ionic character in the solvent thus stabilizes A^- of I_1 more than that of other indicators, for those possibilities are absent.

Fig. 3. Equilibrium characteristics of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene (I_1).

Fig. 4. Equilibrium characteristics of 2-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene (I_2).

Conclusions :

- (i) Since solubilities in aqua-ionic medium are greater than that in pure water and indicator constants are around 7, the synthesized dyes behave as more effective indicator in aqua-ionic solvent systems in comparison to water.
- (ii) Among all the indicators (azo dyes) I₁ shows maximum increase of solubility with increasing concentration of NaNO₃ whereas that of other indicators are relatively less and similar. These seems to be due to the prominent Zwitterion structure of I₁ than that of I₂-I₄.
- (iii) The solvent effect of dissociation equilibrium can be well understood by the relative solvation of all the involved species participating in the equilibrium.

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